

1 **RGMB guidance receptor expression during lineage commitment from pluripotent stem cells.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of RGMB
8 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the
9 human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Elmentaite, R., Kumasaka, N., Roberts, K., Fleming, A., Dann, E., King, H.W., Kleshchevnikov, V.,
12 Dabrowska, M., Pritchard, S., Bolt, L. and Vieira, S.F., 2021. Cells of the human intestinal tract mapped
13 across space and time. *Nature*, 597(7875), pp.250-255.
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28